

Ethics Assessment Form, Ethics Commission, Department of Informatics, Universität Hamburg

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The local Ethics Commission of the Department of Informatics of the Faculty of Mathematics, Informatics and Natural Sciences of Universität Hamburg

Ethics Assessment Form:

Before submitting your research project proposal for approval by the local Ethics Commission of Universität Hamburg's Department of Informatics, please use this questionnaire to think through the potential ethical aspects and challenges of your research project and potential ways of mitigating ethical risks. To apply for approval, please then submit the filled-out and signed form to the ethics commission in time. You can find the submission deadlines and dates for the commission's hearing on the website: <https://www.inf.uni-hamburg.de/home/ethics.html>. You can contact the ethics commission via email on ethikkommission@informatik.uni-hamburg.de

Disclaimer: Ensuring research ethics (and legal compliance) is the responsibility of the researchers conducting the individual research projects. This means it is their task to think through the ethical aspects and potential problems of their research throughout the research process and to incorporate research ethics into their projects' design. This should be done before applying to the local Ethics Commission. The commission can then approve that this has been done appropriately. The questionnaire provided by the Ethics Commission presents a tool for researchers to think through the ethical dimensions of their project.

For all applicants:

Project Title:

Principal Investigator (PI):

Name	Institution/Faculty	Email

Project Funding:

Declaration of Conflict of Interest:

Research Description

1. In about 250-500 words, please provide a brief description of the research project you are seeking the approval of the ethics commission for. Please be aware that members of the commission may not be from your field. Please explain technical terms or use language accessible to people outside your field.
2. What are your research goals?
3. Briefly name and explain your research methods (e.g. experimental, qualitative or quantitative methods). Here you may add material that helps the commission understand the planned procedure such as for instance schematic overviews over the experimental setup.

Please answer where applicable:

Human Participants

4. Does your study involve human participants?
5. Who are the human participants of your study and how do you recruit them?
6. Are there any vulnerable groups among your participants or participants who cannot fully give informed consent, e.g., minors, people with dementia, or other health conditions, and so forth? If yes, how do you take the ethical issues arising from this into consideration?
7. If you are conducting research with vulnerable groups, please explain why particular research with this group is necessary for your research aims and why this research could not be conducted with a non-vulnerable group. Please also explain in which way your research benefits this group and what you do to further this group's well-being.
8. Is there any possibility that your experiment may have a negative impact on the physical or mental health or well-being of the participants? If so, how do you plan to mitigate this risk?

9. Is there any possibility of discovering previously unknown conditions (incidental findings), such as medical diagnoses, and if so, how do you plan to react to such results?

Informed Consent

10. How do you ensure that research participants have full understanding of the research purpose, collected data and its use and the nature of their participation? How do you establish informed consent? Please also submit the informed consent form you plan to use.
11. Are there any hurdles for establishing informed consent in your research or does your research design prohibit the rigorous establishment of informed consent? Please explain how. Please also explain why an alternative research design is not possible for your research purpose. How do you plan to mitigate the negative effects of this circumstance and which mechanism of briefing and debriefing do you have in place?

Data Protection and Privacy

12. Does your study involve the processing of data about people or generated by their activity?
13. Do you collect any personal or personally identifiable data? Do you collect any sensitive data (cf. Art. 9 GDPR)?
14. If so, how do you ensure the protection of this data? How is it stored and transferred? Who will have access?
15. Do you use any third-party providers or services that may have access to research or personal data? Please explain why no alternative ways of data processing are possible and how you plan to mitigate negative effects.

Publication and sharing of data and research results

16. In what form will you publish or distribute your research results, or the data collected? Do you consider the FAIR principles? (Wilkinson, Mark D., et al. "The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship." *Scientific data* 3.1 (2016): 1-9.)
17. How do you anonymize/pseudonymize data? Do any publications include personal or sensitive data or the potential for reidentification or abuse? If so, how do you plan to mitigate risks stemming from this?

Responsible Disclosure

18. Does your research bear the potential to identify cybersecurity risks or vulnerabilities or risks to the security of infrastructures? If so, how does your research contribute to

closing these vulnerabilities? What procedures for responsible disclosure do you intend to follow?

Dual Use

19. Does your research, your research results or publication thereof bear the potential for abuse, malicious use, military use or the violation of laws and personal and human rights in the future? If so, in what way do you plan to mitigate the potential for such dual use?

Other Relevant Information or Issues

20. Are there any other relevant ethical issues, challenges or problems that you wish to bring to the attention of the ethics commission? Is there any other information you find relevant for the ethics assessment?

Declaration

I hereby confirm that the information provided is truthful, accurate and complete.

_____ (Location, Date) ----- Signature: